

South Korean Tourists' Expectation, Satisfaction and Loyalty Relationship

Tolga Gok, Kursad Sayin

Abstract—The aim of this study is to investigate the relationship between expectation, satisfaction and loyalty of South Korean tourists visiting Turkey. In the research, a questionnaire was used as a data collecting tool. The questionnaires are filled by South Korean tourists coming to Turkey through package tours and individual. The survey was conducted in 2014 in Nevsehir (Cappadocia Region) and Istanbul. Tourist guides and agency staff have helped the implementation of surveys. The survey questions are composed of 4 parts, which are “demographic characteristics of tourists”, “travel behavior characteristics”, “perception of expectations on destination attributes” and “perception of destination loyalty”. 5-point Likert type scale including 28 destination attributes was used to measure the expectations of South Korean tourists coming to Turkey. Questions were directed to the tourists to measure the destination loyalty. The questions relating to destination loyalty are “Talking about Turkey to others”, “Recommendation Turkey to others” and “Tourists’ intentions to revisit Turkey”. The basic hypothesis of the research is that there is a statistically significant relationship among expectations, satisfactions and destination loyalty of South Korean tourists coming to Turkey. The results indicated that the expectation had a significant effect on overall satisfaction. In addition it was seen that between overall satisfaction of tourists and destination loyalty had a significant relationship. Based on findings, some suggestions for tour operators and travel agencies were made.

Keywords—Tourist expectation, tourist satisfaction, destination loyalty, destination attributes.

I. INTRODUCTION

IN recent years, fast change and developments in a competitive environment has taken effect especially in tourism sector. By the effect of technological development and global system, the quantitative and qualitative side of touristic activities in the world today has shown an increase. The destinations, desiring to come into prominence and be successful in the intense competitive business atmosphere, have to become aware of the tourists’ expectations and offer the services expected from them, which is inevitable in competitive atmosphere.

After deciding the destination for their holiday, the tourists are known to have some certain expectations related to the destination attributes, and the satisfaction they feel during and after visiting the destination is a function of these expectations [1]-[3].

Understanding the expectations will offer the managers of the destinations and the leaders of the tourism sector the

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important clues how to increase the attractiveness of the destination and improve and market the touristic products and service offered in the destination [4]. Turkey, having a dynamic tourism potential which can cover all the expectations caused by the changes of the world tourism market, has made important progress since 1980s. Turkey, having great share in tourism sector in which there is a continuous development and competition, is keeping on being in search of providing expectations and satisfactions by covering expectations and increasing number of visiting tourists.

Turkey, having natural and cultural wealth, is one of the important destinations in the world tourism with its climate and geographic location. Due to its tourism potential, the number of tourists visiting Turkey has significantly increased recently.

TABLE I
THE NUMBERS OF SOUTH KOREAN TOURISTS VISITING TURKEY IN 2012-2014
(JANUARY-DECEMBER) [5]

Nationality	Years			% Rate of Change	
	2012	2013	2014	2013/2012	2014/2013
South Korea	159 084	187 040	248 910	17,57	33,08

The importance of the Far East market for Turkey in tourism is increasing. Especially, South Korea comes first among the countries sending tourists from Far East to Turkey. According to last three years’ tourism statistic, the number of the tourist coming from South Korea has also increased considerably (Table I). It accounts for approximately 28% of the Far East market. It is thought that the historical proximity of South Korea and Turkey is important for the emergence of this situation

The number of studies on the relationship among expectation, satisfaction and loyalty of visiting tourists from the Far East to Turkey is relatively low. Therefore, this study was implemented to reveal relationship among expectation, satisfaction and loyalty of South Korean Tourists visiting Turkey.

II. LITERATURE

A. Expectation, Satisfaction and Loyalty of Tourists

Tourist satisfaction is important to successful destination marketing because it influences the choice of destination, the consumption of goods and services, and the decision to return [6]. The satisfaction that the tourists feel in a destination is accepted as an important variable to identify the performance of that destination [2]. According to the researches,

satisfaction is a function of both certain expectations related to attributes and the performance of these attributes. Tourists create expectations related to performance of the destinations first and then purchasing and the behavior of utilizing follow it [1]. According to this theory, satisfaction related to the destination forms by the result of comparing the expectations developed about the destinations and the performance perceived about this destination [2]. For this reason, tourist satisfaction can be understood by evaluation and perception of the attributes of the destination [7]. Pizam and his friends [8] claim that satisfaction of the each attributes in the tourism destinations has to be identified to survey the satisfactions in tourism destinations.

There are quite many attributes which can affect the tourists' expectations and satisfactions related to a destination. When we talk about the destination attributes, we mean transportation, accommodation, food and beverage services, entertainment services, the quality and price of the services, communication with the local community and trades people and sightseeing [9]. The attributes related to a tourism destination can be grouped under 6 titles. These are attractiveness (natural and unnatural entities), transportation communication, accommodation, food and beverage, shopping facilities, planned tours, different activities and the other service units (banks, communication tools, health services etc.) [10]. The destination attributes have vital importance for the foreign tourists' coming to some certain destinations. It possible to talk about so many destinations attributes which attract people to some certain destinations. From the literature review, the following thirteen attributes were frequently used in previous studies, namely, (1) Culture & history (monument, heritage, arts, handcraft and ways of life of local people), (2) Landscape (beautiful scenery and natural attractions), (3) Services (shopping, accommodation, food, and transportation), (4) Entertainment, (5) Relaxation, (6) Climate (e.g., pleasant weather), (7) Price (e. g., cost, good value for money), (8) Sport, (9) Safety (personal safety), (10) Local people's attitude toward tourists, (11) Special events and activities, (12) Accessibility (information available), and (13) Adventure. Most of them are also commonly attractive to tourists [11].

Customer satisfaction measures how well a customer's expectations are met. By contrast, customer loyalty measures how likely customers are to return and to spread positive words about destinations to others. Therefore, customer expectations must be met or exceeded to form loyalty [12]. The behavioral interpretation of loyalty includes the act of a consumer who repeatedly buys the same brand. Taking this perspective, some researchers measure loyalty on the basis of the customer's intention to recommend or to repurchase [13]. Various reasons are given for retaining customers: increase sales and profit, reduce marketing and operational costs, provide strong word-of-mouth and create business referrals [14].

The indicators used in the general customer loyalty literature are seen that used in destination loyalty researches in the same way. It was observed that overall satisfaction level in the researches directly affected loyalty [3], [15].

Consequently, as identified by [16], the interpretation of loyalty, in the tourism, refers to tourists' intentions to revisit the destination, and their willingness to recommend it to others.

Consequently, on the basis of review of literature we hypotheses;

- H1. There is a significant relationship between the expectation and the overall satisfaction levels of South Korean tourists visiting Turkey.
- H2. There is a significant relationship between the overall satisfaction and destination loyalty of South Korean tourists visiting Turkey.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Research Objectives

This study has been carried out to survey the expectation and satisfaction levels, and destination loyalty of the tourists coming to Turkey from South Korea. Thus, a great deal of contribution has been supplied to improve the attributes of the destination by determining the expectation, satisfaction and loyalty of incoming tourists. The tourists whose expectations are fulfilled will visit the country again and contribute the introduction of the area by advertising the destinations to his friends.

B. Research Method

First of all, we have performed a comprehensive literature research. The questionnaire has been developed as a data collection tool by making use of the literature research. Questionnaire is in English and Korean. In the questionnaire, there are "demographic questions", "questions regarding the travel behavior of tourists", "a 28-item expectation scale related to the attributes of the destination" and "questions related to destination loyalty" that determine the levels of expectation, satisfactions and destination loyalty of the tourists. At the expectation scale, the participants have been asked to specify their expectation levels (1: very low expectation ...5: very high expectation) related to the attributes of the destinations. As for satisfaction scale; the participants have been asked to specify their overall satisfaction levels (1: very dissatisfied ...5: very satisfied) related to the attributes of the destination. Moreover, the tourists have been asked to answer a question to determine the level of their general satisfaction about the destination. The 3-item scale was designed to understand tourist loyalty. Asked questions to determine the loyalty of the tourists are: (1) talking about their experiences on tour to others, (2) their willingness to recommend Turkey to others, and (3) tourists' intentions to revisit Turkey. Respondents were asked to indicate their agreement level of each item on the 5-point Likert scale anchored by "I completely disagree (=1)" to "I completely agree (=5)".

The questionnaire has been held by using the method of convenience sampling. It has been held in 2014 in Nevsehir (Cappadocia Region) and Istanbul. It has been conducted by the help of tourist guides working at the travel agencies. 127

South Korean tourists have been participating in the questionnaire. 111 useable questionnaires were returned. SPSS 20.0 has been used to analyze the data and frequency, percentage, factor analysis, correlation and regression analyses have been performed. The restriction of the research is that it aims to determine the levels of the expectation, satisfaction and loyalty of the only tourists from South Korean visiting Turkey.

IV. FINDINGS

A. Demographic Characteristics of Tourists

The gender range of the tourists coming from South Korea is that 35.5% of them are women and 64.5 % of them are men. Age range of the participants of the research is that more than half of them are upper 50 (59.5%). The education levels of the visitors are that 63.5% of them have their bachelor's degrees and post graduate degrees. 38% and 24.1 % of them are retired and civil servant respectively. 34.3%, 29.3%, 13.1%, 15.2% and 8.1% of the participants earn 20.000-39.999, 40.000-59.999, more than 80.000, less than 20.000 and 60.000-79.999 USD per year respectively.

B. Travel Behavior Characteristics

All of the participants have come to Turkey by plane. They have been asked how to familiarize the destination; their answers are in this way: 31.2% from internet, 33% from travel agencies. 37.4% of the participants said that they came to Turkey for the first time, and 62.6% of them expressed that they had been to Turkey before. 27.8%, 42.9%, 15.2%, 2.6% and 11.4% of the participants have expressed to stay 1-5 days, 6-10 days, 11-15 days, 16-20 days and more than 20 days in Turkey respectively. 73.1% and 26.9% of comers have stated that they came via travel agents and personal efforts respectively. 40.7% and 23.1% of the participants said that they have chosen Turkey for leisure and cultural reasons respectively. All of the participants have been obviously stayed at hotels. 51.4%, 40.4%, 4.6% and 2.8% of the participants have chosen the bed and breakfast (BB), half board (HB), full board (FB), and all inclusive (AI) forms of accommodation respectively. It has been understood that 65% of the tourists have spent between 2000 - 3000USD to come to Turkey.

C. The Results of Factor Analysis Related to Destination Attributes

Factor analysis was conducted to variables related to destination attributes determining the level of expectations of South Korean tourists coming to Turkey. In the resulted factor analysis, 3 factors were defined and explained 75,89% of variance. These factors were named as follows: (1) destination attractiveness and transportation, (2) communication and (3) tourist attractions and activities. The results of the factor analysis are presented in Table II.

The levels of expectations related to the destination's attributes divided into 3 of were specified at Table III. Having a look at general arithmetic averages, it has been understood that the level of expectations of the tourists about the variables

in the destination attractiveness are high.

TABLE II
 FACTOR ANALYSIS RESULTS RELATED TO DESTINATION

Factors	Variables of Destination Attributes	Factor Loadings
Factor 1	Transportation and Destination Attractiveness	
	Facilities at the destination airport	0,843
	Comfort of traveling between the destination airport and the resort	0,833
	Cleanliness of the destination airport	0,801
	Distance between the resort and the destination airport	0,782
	Speed of check-in/check-out at the destination airport	0,772
	Quality standard of accommodation	0,771
	Attitude of staff working in tourism sector	0,761
	Level of service at accommodation	0,732
	Quality and variety of food	0,724
	Atmosphere in the resort overall	0,720
	Feeling of safety and security	0,719
	Responsiveness to customer complaints	0,693
	Overall value for money	0,673
	Hygiene and sanitation overall	0,640
	Museums and historical places	0,635
Natural environment	0,611	
Factor 2	Communication	
	Brochures in foreign language	0,862
	Signposts in foreign language at the airport	0,844
	Menu in foreign language at accommodation	0,837
	Menu in foreign language in restaurants	0,826
	Written material in foreign language	0,822
Level of communication in foreign language	0,757	
Factor 3	Tourist Attractions and Activities	
	Facilities for children	0,824
	Nightlife and entertainment	0,823
	Shopping facilities	0,799
	Sport facilities	0,761
	Daily tours to other resorts	0,622
	Variety of attractions	0,533
Total		

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy= 0.916; Total Variance Explained at 75,899%; Bartlett's Test of Sphericity: Chi-Square = 3036,096; df= 378; Significance=0.000

The first 3 attributes that have the highest level of expectations of the tourists participating the research are "museums and historical places" (3.97), "natural environment" (3.90) and "Attitude of staff working in tourism sector" (3.80). And the first 3 lowest levels of expectations of the attributes are "nightlife and entertainment" (3.22), "Facilities for children" (3.35) and "Sport facilities" (3.37). It is seen that the lowest level of tourist expectations of the attributes are related to the variables of tourist attractions and activities.

D. The Satisfactions of Tourists

The results related to overall satisfaction level from destination was presented in Table IV. According to this, it is possible to suggest 65.69% of the South Korean Tourist's participating the research is satisfied with Turkey. But 26.46% of them are midlevel satisfied. Approximately one-quarter of

the tourists were midlevel satisfied. When considered in conjunction with the non-satisfaction, it is necessary to investigate its cause.

TABLE III
DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS OF LEVEL OF TOURIST EXPECTATION

	Destination Attributes	Mean	SD
1	Quality standard of accommodation	3,59	0,92
2	Level of service at accommodation	3,59	0,96
3	Feeling of safety and security	3,78	0,89
4	Attitude of staff working in tourism sector	3,80	0,95
5	Natural environment	3,90	0,96
6	Overall value for money	3,54	0,99
7	Atmosphere in the resort overall	3,68	0,96
8	Quality and variety of food	3,72	1,03
9	Responsiveness to customer complaints	3,66	0,97
10	Hygiene and sanitation overall	3,77	0,96
11	Sport facilities	3,37	1,07
12	Nightlife and entertainment	3,22	1,23
13	Variety of attractions	3,76	1,04
14	Facilities for children	3,35	1,10
15	Shopping facilities	3,43	0,98
16	Daily tours to other resorts	3,64	0,99
17	Museums and historical places	3,97	0,93
18	Written material in foreign language	3,68	0,97
19	Brochures in foreign language	3,70	0,97
20	Menu in foreign language in restaurants	3,76	0,98
21	Menu in foreign language at accommodation	3,69	0,95
22	Signposts in foreign language at the airport	3,74	0,95
23	Level of communication in foreign language	3,77	0,95
24	Cleanliness of the destination airport	3,65	1,03
25	Speed of check-in/check-out at the destination airport	3,73	0,89
26	Facilities at the destination airport	3,77	0,93
27	Distance between the resort and the destination airport	3,65	0,97
28	Comfort of traveling between the destination airport and the resort	3,77	1,01

The values of arithmetic mean were calculated by excluding those who didn't express their opinion. Scale: Very low expectation=1. Very high expectation=5 The reliability analysis result of this question is found to be as Alpha value=0.975. It may be accepted as a highly reliable scale [17].

TABLE IV
OVERALL SATISFACTION (N: 102)

Satisfaction Level	N	%
Very dissatisfied	1	0,98
Somewhat dissatisfied	7	6,86
Fairly well satisfied	27	26,47
Very satisfied	43	42,16
Completely satisfied	24	23,53

Arithmetic mean: 3,804; Sd: 0.912; Scale: Very dissatisfied: 1 Completely satisfied: 5

E. The Relationship between Expectation and Overall Satisfaction Levels of Tourists

The correlation analysis has been used to reveal relation between expectation level and overall satisfaction. Means, standard deviations and correlation coefficients among variables related expectation levels and overall satisfaction were given in Table V. Cronbach's Alpha coefficients of used scales at research are significant level ($\alpha > 0.70$).

According to results of correlation analysis in Table V, a

positive and meaningful relation has been revealed between expectation level related sub-dimensions of destination attributes (Destination Attractiveness and Transportation ($r=0,369$; $p<0,01$), Communication ($r=0,330$; $p<0,01$), Tourist Attractions and Activities ($r=0,200$; $p<0,05$), Overall expectation ($r=0,344$; $p<0,01$), and overall satisfaction.

TABLE V
DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS AND CORRELATIONS AMONG VARIABLES

	Mean	Std. Error	1	2	3	4	5
1. Destination attractiveness and transportation	3,73	0,77	1				
2. Communication	3,73	0,89	0,660**	1			
3. Tourist attractions and activities	3,46	0,89	0,663**	0,595**	1		
4. Overall expectation	3,68	0,74	0,955**	0,815**	0,805**	1	
5 Overall satisfaction	3,80	0,91	0,369**	0,330**	0,200*	0,344**	1

Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed). Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level. (2-tailed)

The regression analyses have been carried out for determining relation between expectation level related sub-dimensions of destination attributes and overall satisfaction. As it seems in Table VI, there is a positive and meaningful relation between expectation level related sub-dimensions of destination attributes and overall satisfaction. This result supports correlation analysis results.

The regression analysis has been used to determine whether the expectation level related sub-dimensions of destination attributes affected to overall satisfaction or not.

TABLE VI
THE REGRESSION ANALYSIS RESULTS BETWEEN THE EXPECTATION LEVEL RELATED SUB-DIMENSIONS OF DESTINATION ATTRIBUTES AND OVERALL SATISFACTION

Independent Variables	B	Std. Error	β	t	Sig.
Constant	1,690	0,475		3,558	0,001
1. Destination Attractiveness and Transportation	0,550	0,169	0,441	3,259	0,002*
2. Communication	0,128	0,142	0,115	0,900	0,370
3. Tourist Attraction and Activities	-0,120	0,138	-0,111	-0,869	0,387

$R=0,456$; $R^2=0,208$; Adjusted $R^2=0,182$; $F=7,803$; $P=0,001$ * Dependent variable: Overall Satisfaction, * $p<0,01$

When sub-dimensions of destination attributes (Destination Attractiveness and Transportation, Communication, Tourist Attraction and Activities) was entered as independent variables, it has been shown that only "Destination Attractiveness and Transportation" affected to overall satisfaction as positive and meaningful statistically (Adjusted $R^2=0,208$). The hypothesis of H1 is accepted.

The regression analyses have been carried out for determining relation between overall expectation level related

destinations attributes and overall satisfaction. As it seems in Table VII, there is a positive and meaningful relation between overall expectation levels related destination attributes and overall satisfaction. This result supports correlation analysis results.

TABLE VII

THE REGRESSION ANALYSIS RESULTS BETWEEN OVERALL EXPECTATION LEVEL RELATED DESTINATION ATTRIBUTES AND OVERALL SATISFACTION

Independent Variables	B	Std. Error	β	t	Sig.
Constant	2,182	0,452		4,827	0,000
Overall expectation	0,439	0,120	0,344	3,649	0,000*

R=0,344; R²=0,119; Adjusted R²=0,110; F=13,316; P=0,000* Dependent variable: Overall Satisfaction, *p<0,01

When overall expectation was entered as independent variable, it has been shown that overall expectation affected to overall satisfaction as positive and meaningful statistically (Adjusted R²=0,119).

The results of regression and correlation analysis proved the argument that there is a positive and meaningful relation between expectation and overall satisfaction of the South Korean tourists visiting Turkey.

F. The Destination Loyalty of Tourists

Three questions were asked related to the destination loyalty to tourists. The results related to the destination loyalty were presented in Table VIII. When the arithmetic means are examined, "Recommendation Turkey to others" item related to destination loyalty is higher than others. "Tourists' intentions to revisit Turkey" item has the lowest mean.

TABLE VIII

DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS OF DESTINATION LOYALTY

Variables	Mean	SD
1 Talking about Turkey to others	3,87	1,04
2 Recommendation Turkey to others	3,88	1,01
3 Tourists' intentions to revisit Turkey	3,51	1,16

The values of arithmetic mean were calculated by excluding those who didn't express their opinion. Scale: "I completely disagree=1", "I completely agree=5". The reliability analysis result of this question is found to be as Alpha value=0.914. It may be accepted as a highly reliable scale [17].

G. The Relationship between Overall Satisfaction and Destination Loyalty of Tourists

The correlation analysis has been used to reveal relation between overall satisfaction level and sub-dimensions of destination loyalty. Means, standard deviations and correlation coefficients among variables related overall satisfaction levels and sub-dimensions of destination loyalty were given in Table IX. Cronbach's Alpha coefficients of used scales at research are significant level ($\alpha > 0.70$).

According to results of correlation analysis in Table IX, a positive and meaningful relation has been revealed between overall satisfaction level related sub-dimensions of destination loyalty (Talking about Turkey to others ($r=0,784$; $p<0,01$), Recommendation Turkey to others ($r=0,711$; $p<0,01$), Tourists' intentions to revisit Turkey ($r=0,646$; $p<0,01$)).

TABLE IX

DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS AND CORRELATIONS AMONG VARIABLES

	Mean	Std. Error	1	2	3	4
1. Overall Satisfaction	3,80	0,91	1			
2. Talking about Turkey to others	3,87	1,04	0,784**	1		
3. Recommendation Turkey to others	3,88	1,01	0,711**	0,857**	1	
4. Tourists' intentions to revisit Turkey	3,51	1,16	0,646**	0,715**	0,755**	1

Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level. (2-tailed)

V. CONCLUSION

The following results were reached in the research about South Korean tourists visiting Turkey. The participants' expectations related to destination attributes are analyzed according to factor analyses under 3 dimensions (Destination Attractiveness and Transportation, Communication, Tourist Attractions and Activities). According to this, having a look at the arithmetic overall, generally the Destination Attractiveness and Transportation is the highest level of expectations. The second best is the Communication and the third is Tourist Attractions and Activities. When each variable in each destination attribute is taken into consideration, we see that the first three highest the level of the expectation is about the dimension of Destination Attractiveness and Transportation. These are "museums and historical places", "natural environment" and "Attitude of staff working in tourism sector". The dimension of Tourist Attractions and Activities has the lowest level of expectation. The variables related to the dimension of Tourist Attractions and Activities have also the lowest level of the expectation among the variables related to the other dimensions. The subjects having the lowest level of the expectation related to Tourist Attractions and Activities are "nightlife and entertainment", "Facilities for children" and "Sport facilities". That the tourists are usually old and have no children may cause to decrease the level of expectation about these subjects. 74% of the people participating in the research are clearly understood that they are generally satisfied with the destination. It is pleasing that 61% of South Korean tourists coming to Turkey stated that they will advise the others Turkey. According to the correlation analyses performed to identify the relation between the levels of expectation and satisfaction, we identified a positive and meaningful relation between the level of the overall satisfaction and the overall expectation, and 3 dimensions related to the attributes of destination.

According to results of the regression analyses performed to identify the effects on the levels of the overall satisfaction and expectation related to sub-dimension of the attributes of the destination, the dimension of the Destination Attractiveness and Transportation has been identified to affect the level of the overall satisfaction positively. According to regression analyses performed to identify the level of the overall satisfaction related to the attributes of the destination, it is seen that the overall expectation effects the overall satisfaction

positively. According to the results of the correlation and regression analyses performed, there is a statistically meaningful relation between the levels of expectation and satisfaction, and our principle hypothesis has been accepted. These findings coincide with the studies performed by [18]-[20] in literature.

In addition, tourist satisfaction is very important for customer loyalty. In this study, a very high correlation between customer loyalty and satisfaction of tourists has been identified. Approximately 64% of South Korean tourists have said they would talk to others about the Turkey. 65% of them have mentioned that they would recommend to others. 50% of tourists have told that they would visit Turkey again.

At the end of the questionnaire, there are two matters that the guests are complaining the most; lack of food diversity to appeal to the taste buds and long distances, causing great waste of time, between the locations you visited in destination.

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